

INTEGRATED HOSPITALITY SERVICES AND GUESTS' PATRONAGE OF LUXURY HOTELS IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

In Nigeria today, customer cultivation and retention in the harsh post COVID-19 business environment, aggravated by problems occasioned by oil subsidy removal, is a challenge and concern to hotel managers as their survival depends on deployment of appropriate response strategies. The aim of this research, therefore, was to evaluate the effect of integrated hospitality services on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study; the population of which comprised 246 guests drawn from 10 luxury hotels during the 2023 Christmas festive season in Port Harcourt. Primary data were collected from a well-structured questionnaire, administered on the guests and complimented by secondary data from academic journal papers. Statistical tools for data analyses include; simple percentage, mean scores and standard deviation as well as Multiple Regression Analysis. The findings of the descriptive analysis revealed integrated hospitality services delivery competence and high guests' patronage during the period of our investigation. Multiple regression analysis showed that all the 4 indicators of integrated hospitality services (accommodation, restaurant services, nightclub entertainment and gymnasium service delivery positively and significantly in varied degree, influenced guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Based on the finding, it was concluded that integrated hospitality service dimensions had significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt. In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, it was recommended that the current service standard should be maintained or improved upon in line with the changing customer preferences and that new guests should be informed of all the services available in the fusion facility.

Keywords:

Integrated hospitality services, guests' patronage

1. Introduction

The hospitality sector is an important component of the tourism industry. It provides most of services that tourists and travellers need at the destination. Hospitality services include accommodations, foods and beverages, entertainments, etc in a warm, courteous, receptive and liberal manner (Ahmario&Gilson, 2018). One of the important constituents of the hospitality industry in the accommodation category that has impacted positively on national and global economy is the hotel sub-sector. A hotel is a commercial establishment that provides lodging accommodations and various services to travelers, tourists, or guests at a profit (Tahiri, *et al.*, 202).

The hotel business has evolved significantly over the centuries from something that began with basic inns and taverns, catering to travelers' basic needs through the Industrial Revolution. Progressively, it has grown into modern grand hotels that offered a wide range of budget and luxury and amenities that emphasize class, style, comfort, safety, convenience and personalization of services (Esthelo, 2015). The revolutions or innovations in the hotel sector have also been characterized by the introduction of chain hotels that emphasize standardized and uniform services to the advent of Luxury and themed hotels offering diverse experiences. In recent times, the digital revolution and online booking platforms have changed how guests make reservations (Mattsson & Orfila-Sintes, 2014; Scott, 2018). Thus, from humble beginnings to today's diverse, tech-savvy, and customer-centric establishments, the hotel business has come a long way, reflecting evolving traveler expectations and industry innovations in order to stay competitive.

As competition intensifies in the various hotel market segments across the globe, the snack for survival and profitable business operation in the face of daunting tasks in the ever-dynamic business environment has informed the designing of creative and innovative models of hotel management. One of such models is the integrated hospitality services whereby various independent hospitality operations and facilities such as accommodation, restaurant, nightclub, gymnasium, spa/wellness centres and ancillary services are brought together under one hotel roof (Juumps,2017). In the literature, other semantics and synonyms such as 'fusion facilities', 'full service hotel' and 'one-stop hotel' are used to denote integrated hospitality services. Horace (2021) asserts that integration of hospitality services under one facility is a new concept of modern hospitality marketing that promotes motion and financial economy for customers as well as revenue generation and increased profit for the organization through patronage.

Guests' patronage describes a customer's repeat visit to the same hotel or any other hospitality organization or a customer's sustained purchase behavior toward a particular brand of hospitality product, service or facility (Mueolo&Sygha, 2018). Consequently, hotel guest patronage has assumed a pivotal role in the success and survival of any hotel business in both developed and developing economies, depressed or growing economy.

Research into customer patronage in the service industry has increased dramatically in recent years, and this increase has been aggravated by the increasing need for the survival of the industry in an ever dynamic environment fraught with challenges that affect the service industries and by extension, influence their strategies (Jones, *et al.*, 2016). One of such challenges is guest retention in the face of declining purchasing power and low discretionary income in Nigeria with attendant poor leisure culture. These maladies in recent times have been exacerbated due to economic fluctuations, the advent of Corona Virus pandemic, naira devaluation and removal of petroleum subsidies. The impact of low patronage is acutely felt during economic downturns when disposable income dwindles, leading to a decline in travel and hospitality spending. In such periods, hotels grapple with heightened competition, necessitating innovative strategies to attract guests and retain them.

In the bid to stay afloat the stormy economic water and survive, some luxury hotels have introduced fusion facilities strategies whereby integrated hospitality under one roof, one-stop setting services are offered to guests. Previous studies have linked integrated distribution trade and fusion services in retail and wholesale trading with positive outcome such as increase in sales volume and profit(Hiese& Zunkens,2014; Semade et al, 2016; Ekiyo and Ekaemem, 2018). However, there is limited knowledge in the literature regarding integrated hospitality service delivery and guests' patronage in the Nigerian luxury hotel market scale, thus creating a gap that needs to be bridged. Therefore, this study was undertaken to examine the effect of integrated hospitality services and guests' patronage in luxury hotels in Rivers State.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Clarification

The Concept of Integrated Hospitality Services

Integrated hospitality services can be regarded as a set of complementary or supplementary services and facilities that are offered by a hotel or a hotel chain to its guests under one roof or within a close proximity (Juumps, 2019). It is viewed as an innovative strategy whereby various hospitality operations and facilities such as accommodation, restaurant, nightclub, cinema, gymnasium, spa/wellness centres, etc are brought together under one hotel roof (Os-Khali,,2017). In the literature, other semantics and synonyms such as 'fusion facilities', 'full service hotel' and 'one-stop hotel', 'all-inclusive hotel' are used to denote integrated hospitality service facility (Juump,2019). Ameenson and Gilles (2016) assert that integration of hospitality services under one facility is a new concept of modern hospitality marketing.

The main purpose of integrated hospitality services is to create value for hotel guests by providing them with convenience, comfort, variety, and personalization. This integration is designed to create a one-stop destination for guests, fostering convenience and satisfaction. The concept aims to address the evolving needs and expectations of modern travellers by offering a seamless and immersive experience. Integrated hospitality services can also create value for hoteliers by increasing their revenue through upselling and cross-selling, reducing their costs through economies of scale and scope, and enhancing their reputation and loyalty through service differentiation and quality.

The concept of integrated hospitality services is inspired by the one-stop-shop model that is widely used in distributive retailing business as expressed through departmental stores, supermarkets, and malls (Gebreselassie & Baku, 2020; Joshi & Dasani, 2020). The idea is to offer a variety of products and services that cater to different needs and preferences of customers in one location, under one facility, thereby saving them time, money, and effort. Similarly, integrated hospitality services aim to offer a variety of hospitality services and facilities that cater to different needs and preferences of hotel guests in one location, thereby saving them time, money, and effort.

Dimensions of Integrated Hospitality Services

The concept of integrated hospitality services has evolved to encompass a spectrum of dimensions, each contributing to the creation of a seamless and comprehensive guest experience. These dimensions represent a strategic fusion of various services under one roof, transforming hotels into multifaceted amenities tailored to meet the diverse needs of modern travellers. The dimensions of integrated hospitality service provision as used in the context of this study are as follow:

Gymnasium Service Provision

According to a survey by Hotels.com (2018), 56% of travellers consider a gym as a must-have amenity when choosing a hotel, and 46% of them would pay extra for it. In recent years, there has been a notable shift in consumer preferences towards wellness and healthy lifestyles. Gymnasium services align with this trend, offering guests the opportunity to maintain their fitness routines even while traveling for business or leisure.

Temby (2018) highlighted and explained some of the gymnasium services that hotels can offer which include:

i. A gymnasium with modern equipment, such as treadmills, elliptical, bikes, rowers, weights and well-maintained, clean, and safe-to-use resistance machines. The gymnasium should also have adequate space, ventilation, lighting, and music.

ii. Trainers who can assist the guests and customers with their fitness goals, provide personalized guidance, and ensure proper form and technique. The trainers should be certified, experienced, and friendly. They should also be able to offer different types of training, such as cardio, strength, flexibility, balance, and functional.

iii. Classes and programs that cater to different levels of fitness, interests, and schedules. The classes and programs should be varied, engaging, and fun. They should also be led by qualified instructors who can motivate and instruct the participants. Some examples of classes and programs are yoga, pilates, Zumba, HIIT, circuit training, boot camp, and personal training.

iv. Spa services that complement the gymnasium services and provide relaxation and rejuvenation for the guests and customers. The spa services should include massages, facials, manicures, pedicures, and sauna. The spa services should be performed by licensed and skilled therapists who can deliver a soothing and satisfying experience. The spa facilities should be clean, comfortable, and inviting.

Nightclub Entertainment

Nightclub entertainment is an important aspect of the hospitality industry, as it can attract and retain customers, increase revenue, and enhance the hotel's image and reputation. One of the concepts that can be used to understand the role of nightclub entertainment in the integrated hospitality model is the night-time economy. The night-time economy (NTE) represents a multifaceted aspect of urban life, encompassing a spectrum of economic activities that unfold during the evening and night hours. Hall et al. (2016) underscore the significance of understanding the dynamics of the NTE, emphasizing its implications for both urban development and the hospitality industry. The night-time economy represents a compelling and complex urban phenomenon.

Different segments of customers may have different preferences and expectations for nightlife entertainment, depending on their age, gender, culture, lifestyle, and purpose of travel. For example, young and single travellers may prefer a lively and trendy nightclub with a variety of music genres, while older and married travellers may prefer a more relaxed and elegant lounge with live jazz or classical music. Similarly, business travellers may seek a quiet and comfortable place to network and socialize with colleagues or clients, while leisure travellers may look for a fun and exciting place to enjoy with their friends or family. Therefore, hotel managers need to identify their target market segments and understand their needs and wants for nightclub entertainment (Jones, *et al.*, 2016).

Restaurant Service Provision

Restaurant services are an essential component of luxury hotels, as they provide guests with a variety of dining options, experiences, and cuisines that reflect the hotel's brand, quality, and standards. Restaurant services in luxury hotels can range from full silver service in a fine dining restaurant, where the dishes are served at the table by waiters with service spoons and forks, to a self-service buffet, where guests collect their own food from the counter (Hotel Management Tips, 2023). Some luxury hotels also offer room service, where guests can order dishes from the hotel's restaurants or a special menu and enjoy them in the comfort of their own rooms.

One of the main characteristics of restaurant services in luxury hotels is the high level of personalization and customization that they offer to guests. According to EHL Insights (2022), luxury hospitality is redefining itself as "back to basics" with a focus on authenticity, establishing real one-on-one relationships, the importance of service and personalization, as well as the value and uniqueness offered through artistic design and craftsmanship, use of celebrated artists; and quality in all things. For example, some luxury hotels provide guests with a personal chef who can prepare dishes according to their preferences, dietary requirements, or special occasions. Other luxury hotels allow guests to choose their own ingredients, cooking methods, or presentation styles from a variety of options.

Another characteristic of restaurant services in luxury hotels is the diversity and innovation that they showcase in terms of cuisines, concepts, and atmospheres. Luxury hotels often collaborate with renowned chefs, restaurateurs, or brands to create exclusive and distinctive dining experiences for their guests.

Accommodation

As the core of hospitality services, accommodation is more than mere provision of a place to rest; it forms the bedrock of a holistic and immersive guest experience. In the paradigm of integrated hospitality services, the concept of accommodation undergoes a transformative journey, evolving from a basic necessity to a dynamic dimension that sets the tone for an establishment's identity. Accommodation has a multifaceted nature, having significant and innovative impact on the overall guest journey. Accommodation serves as the foundational pillar upon which the entire guest experience is constructed. Beyond providing a physical space for rest, contemporary accommodation offerings are designed to align with the diverse preferences and expectations of modern travellers. In the realm of integrated hospitality services, accommodation becomes a canvas for immersive experiences, reflecting the essence and ethos of the establishment (Davidson, *et al.*, 2011; Shahid & Paul, 2022).

The concept extends beyond physical spaces to include digital innovations, such as smart room technologies, enhancing convenience and personalization. Accommodation plays a pivotal role in shaping the strategic positioning of a hospitality establishment. The style, theme, and amenities associated with accommodation offerings contribute to the overall identity of the hotel. Savvy establishments leverage accommodation as a means of differentiation, creating unique selling propositions that resonate with specific target markets and contribute to the establishment's market positioning (Charman, & Heron, 2015; Walker, 2021).

The Concept of Guest Patronage

Guest patronage represents the choice of guests to consistently choose a particular hotel or service provider for their accommodation and related needs. Guest patronage is influenced by a range of factors, including the quality of services, overall guest experience, value for money, and the establishment's ability to meet evolving customer expectations (Ewanlen, 2021; Susskind, & Viccari, 2011; Singh & Nika, 2019).

Optimizing guest patronage requires strategic operational considerations. From effective staff training programs to leveraging technology for personalized experiences, and the continuous refinement of service offerings based on guest feedback, operational excellence becomes a cornerstone for encouraging guest loyalty. Establishments that prioritize on-going improvements in their operations create an environment that fosters trust and encourages patrons to choose them consistently. Guest satisfaction emerges as a significant catalyst for guest patronage. A satisfied guest is more likely to become a repeat customer, and their positive experiences contribute to the establishment's reputation, attracting new patrons. Integrated hospitality services that consistently deliver high levels of guest satisfaction create a virtuous cycle, where happy patrons become brand ambassadors, advocating for the establishment and contributing to increased patronage (Simpeh, et al., 2011).

Theoretical Foundation of the Study

The Disconfirmation of Expectations Theory

The theoretical anchor of this study is the expectancy-disconfirmation paradigm propounded by Oliver (1980). Drawing on the shortcomings of the early theories of consumer satisfaction, Oliver (1980) proposed the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) as the most promising theoretical framework for the assessment of customer satisfaction, a precursor to customer patronage in a competitive business environment. The model implies that consumers purchase goods and services with pre-purchase expectations about the anticipated performance. The expectation level then becomes a standard for judging the product. That is, once the product or service is used, outcomes are compared against expectations. If the outcome matches the expectation, confirmation occurs. Disconfirmation occurs where there is a difference between expectations and outcomes. A customer is either satisfied or dissatisfied as a result of positive or negative difference between expectations and perceptions. Thus, when service performance is better than what the customer had initially expected, there is a positive disconfirmation between expectations and performance resulting from satisfaction (Bin-Nordin, 2008). Therefore, it could be argued that in the hospitality industry context, guest satisfaction or dissatisfaction is influenced by the perceived quality of service experience which also determines tourist behavior in the industry.

The theory is very useful to this study because the results of continuous customer satisfaction monitoring can serve as an input for trend analysis and strategic discussions regarding the development of an inclusive hospitality facility. The ultimate goals of monitoring satisfaction is through patronage by solicitation of customers feedback, service reviews and ultimately increasing the competitiveness of a given hotel. Furthermore, previous studies on customer satisfaction or patronage had also adopted this theory to explain the phenomenon of their works as shown in Marinao (2017), Zehner (2016); Dmitrovic, Cvelbar, Kolar, Brencic, Ograjens̃ek, and Z̃abkar (2006).

Empirical Review and Hypotheses Development

Many empirical studies have established the interaction between integrated service provision (fusion facilities, one-stop shop, all-inclusive, full-service, integrated hospitality services) and patronage

across various industrial, organizational and geographical contexts. This sub-section of the study presents a review of the influence or interaction between the dimensions of integrated hospitality service provision and guests patronage in previous empirical studies from which we derived our hypotheses formulation.

Gymnasium Service Provision on Guests Patronage

Mzengi (2017) assessed the impacts of hotel recreational services on guests' satisfaction in the case of Gold Crest Hotel, Mwanza City. Using a sample size that included 212 customers drawn through the stratified and purposive sampling technique, the results from the case study revealed that the Gold Crest Hotel lagged on the provision of modern recreational equipment and gym services. The study attributed low patronage, among other factors to the absence of recreational equipment and gymnasium services. Absence of good recreational equipment at Gold Crest Hotel if not addressed would potentially lead to customer turnover; wherein the customers switched to other hotels due to dissatisfaction.

Jennings (2007) examined sport-based tourism, sport leisure and recreational experience. The aim of this study was to present an overview of a number of aerobic-based experience induced by sport leisure and recreation within a variety of gymnastic environment. This study investigated physical exercise-based experience associated with stable, movable, and moving platform and the attendant water-based sport/activities such as sailing, motorboat, surfing and windsurfing, kayaking, scuba, diving, jetski as well as their impact on leisure and recreational experience. Data were analyzed with appropriate statistical tools. The finding established a strong and positive correlation between the provision of adequate and high quality water sport rental services and memorable beach experience in terms of visitors' well-being enhancement through relaxation and entertainment that the beach and ocean recreational activities offer the visitors.

Akubo (2016) carried out a study to test the proposition that customer perception of recreational quality of equipment and services of fitness centres can significantly influence fitness centre brand choice and loyalty. The result of data collected from 218 customers of fitness centres in Abuja a strong correlation between the availability of modern recreational equipment, instructors competence and behaviour, safe environment, ambience and location. Drawing from the foregoing, our first hypothesis is formulated thus:

H1; Gymnasium service provision has a positive and significant effect on guests patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Nightclub Entertainment Provision and Guests' Patronage

Wang and Heng (2019) investigated night time entrepreneurial ventures and customers' patronage in Shanghai and business districts in China in 15 business ventures involving 1850 customers over a period of three months. Patrons were selected from the age bracket of 18 yrs-50 with basic education and an understanding as well as involving in night time life. The analysed data revealed that night club entertainment was rated among young people as the major organized night time recreational activity.

In a similar vein, an important study conducted by Seaman and Horace(207) in full-service hotel facility to customers satisfaction and revisit intention in Maldrid hotel sector. The study made use of 218 business and leisure guests. Using the structural equation modelling technique, the result of the study indicated the expected every luxury hotel to incorporate a nightclub into their operations.

Regarding their satisfaction with the available facilities, data analysis revealed a correlation between nightclub entertainment and revisit intention. This therefore implies that hotels customers, especially the young-at heart and fun-loving ones patronize a hotel facility with a discoteque

Kukoyi and Iwuagwu (2018) researched into hospitality service delivery and customer satisfaction in recreational centres in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study which involved 380 young fun seekers was to rate the importance of hospitality services as perceived by their market segments. Using the spearman rank order correlation technique, the analysed data indicated that among other facilities, nightclub entertainment was highly rated by respondents as a key relaxation avenue in Lagos state. Based on the above review, our second hypothesis is thus proposed:

H2: Nightclub entertainment provision has a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Restaurant Service Provision and Guests' Patronage

Abel (2017) conducted a study on hotel service delivery competence and customer loyalty in fast-food organizations in Delta State in Nigeria. The objective of the study was to determine how service context, personnel attitude and supporting technology affected the competitiveness of the fast-food sector. The finding showed that the use of the digital platform for food service delivery positively and significantly influenced guest satisfaction, patronage and revisit intention.

Yasash and Aminu (2016) assessed the impact of food service quality on Hotel brand loyalty Teran. The purpose of the study was to investigate the behavioural and attitudinal brand loyalty for quick service fast food restaurant. Results showed that there is a positive influence of menu assortment, quality of food delivery on attitude-based loyalty. One critical study conducted by Janeh and Ibrahim (2016) sought to test the proposition of the link between restaurant service delivery and brand loyalty; the mediation effect of brand passion, brand affection and self-brand connection. The result of the survey collected from 355 respondents using an online panel in the UK revealed that compared to staff behaviour, quality of food and beverage and physical environment tended to have a stronger and more significant effect on the three elements of brand passion, brand affection and self-brand connection.

Adeoye and Babatunde (2015) carried out a study on hotel service delivery, and guest revisits intention in the hotel sector. Drawing the inference from 357 guests of 3- star hotels using questionnaires for data collection, revealed that contact personnel attitude, courtesy, food and beverage service availability and house -keeping practices correlated positively with guest satisfaction, intention to revisit in the future as well as positive word -of—month. Consequent upon the above review, our third hypotheses was formulated to test the proposition :

H3: Restaurant service provision has a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria

Accommodation and Guest Patronage

In a recent empirical study conducted by Adesope, Obadimu, Oguntoye, Olusesi, and Oyewo (2023), the general purpose of the research was to investigate hotel patronage and the challenges confronting the hotel industry in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Employing a multistage sampling technique, the study aimed to select both staff and customers patronizing the hotels, although specific details of the population and sampling techniques were not provided in the abstract. The study utilized a well-structured questionnaire and scheduled interviews as data collection instruments to elicit information

from both staff and customers. One of the key findings was that "accommodation" emerged as the highest-rated factor influencing hotel patronage, while other factors, such as security, power supply, and water supply, were also significant considerations for customers in choosing hotels.

The study by Kim et al. (2017) was on destinations and accommodations in Saginaw, Bridgeport, Birch Run, Chesaning, and Frankenmuth in Michigan. Hotel accommodation was one of the factors that had a significant influence on guests' satisfaction ratings. These findings did not actually ignore the presence of push factors.

The study of Lacap (2014) on the competitiveness and sustainability of the hotel industry in Pampanga revealed that the accommodation (good hotel rooms and facilities) to enhance relaxation and good sleep quality had a significant impact on the sustaining customer of the hotel. In the light of the review, our fourth hypothesis is stated thus:

H4: Accommodation has a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria

3. Methodology

Research Design and Sampling

The survey research design was adopted for the study to aid the researcher to find answers to the research questions of the study and to test the hypotheses through the collection and analysis of primary data on the effect of integrated hospitality services on guests' patronage across a large spectrum of luxury hotels in Rivers State. The general aim of selecting a proper research design is to conduct an empirical investigation in such a way that answers the research questions and for the test of hypotheses of the study (Onodugo, Ugwuonah & Ebinne, 2010).

The population of this study comprised of domestic and international guests that were available at luxury hotels during the Christmas festive period, December, 2023 when the study was conducted. Diesamm (2012) has noted that in the context of the tourism and hospitality industry, the population of research involving customers is always large, unpredictable and mobile or transient. It is often not fixed. Consequently, it was not possible to predetermine the actual population size of this study, as it was infinite and unknown. The survey was conducted at the 10 luxury hotels in Port Harcourt during the 2023 festive period (Christmas season). There are 10 registered luxury hotels in Port Harcourt which include Hotel Presidential, Novotel, Golden Tulip Hotel, Osborn La Palm Hotel, Villa Tuscany Hotel, Juanita Hotel, Ogiye's place, Xteem Luxury Hotel and Portland Resort and Suite (www.hotel.com, 2022). These hotels were chosen because of their status as full-service characteristics and customer-drawing power as well as international dispositions. The study sample size was statistically determined after which the researcher adopted the purposive sampling method to select a sample of two hundred and forty six (246) hotel guests (repeat visitors) based on his judgment and on-the-spot accessibility, availability and willingness of the hotel guests to participate in the study during the researcher's visits to the facilities. Our sample size is consistent with the extant suggestion of Roscoe (1975 cited in Aliman et al., 2016) that a sample of more than 30 and less than 500 is sufficient for most research in the Social Sciences of which hospitality is a subset.

Data Collection Methods/Instrumentation

Two types of data were involved in this study, namely: primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained first hand from the luxury hotel guests had visited the same facility in the past. Primary data were complemented by secondary data obtained from relevant academic journals. The data of the study was largely quantitative as it involved quantifiable characteristics as expressed through

measurement and statistical analysis. Our data did not involve interviews, videos, photography and other qualitative elements.

The primary data collection method considered for this study was the questionnaire. The researcher recognizes the fact that the questionnaire accounts significantly for the success of any survey. This research instrument was adopted for the study because of its cost-effectiveness and time-saving considerations.

The questionnaire was the primary data collection instrument considered for this study. A questionnaire is a set of specific questions that are constructed and used by the researcher in obtaining information from the respondents (Makinde 2015). The questionnaire is one of the most used instrument of survey research (Ezejelue, Ogwo&Nkamnebe, 2008). The researcher and 5 (five) research assistants administered copies of questionnaires on business and leisure guests of the luxury hotel after approval by the relevant hotel manager or supervisor having been briefed by the researcher on the purpose of the study. However, questionnaire administration and retrieval through personal contact or third party was guided by ethical considerations and the hotels' policy on guests' privacy. The reason for focusing on hotel guests is because hospitality service delivery is largely people-oriented as they involve customers and service personnel. As such, the quality of hospitality service delivery should be evaluated from the lenses of their customers. This is because no service provider may admit that he/she is not effective in serving its target market relative to the competition.

The questionnaire of this study was structured into four (4) sections: Section A presents the guests' demographic profile. Section B of the instrument consists of structured items on the dimensions of integrated hospitality services. Section C guests patronage.

The dependent and independent variables were measured on the 5-point Likert Scale, and the response scales for each statement in the survey questionnaire are 5-Strongly Agree, 4 –Agree, 3-Undecided, 2-Disagree, 1-Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire items of the variables are modified from previous studies based on their relevance and appropriateness to the present study.

Validity / Reliability of Instrument

In this study, face validity was adopted the research instrument used was ascertained through expert opinions(hospitality operation managers and hospitality marketing scholars)based on their experience in the industry and academia respectively.Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method was used to analyze the responses from the study. The researcher subjected the responses obtained from the survey to testing the reliability via IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 21.0. The resultant values for all the constructs were greater 0.70 which is considered reliable since 0.50 is the minimum value for accepting the reliability test. Nunnally (1978) asserts that Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient with large values indicates a positive correlation and by extension, an acceptable degree of reliability.

Operational Measures of the Variables

Integrated hospitality services and guests' patronage were the two constructs of the study. The independent variable (integrated hospitality services) consists of 4 dimensions which are crucial to the sector. They are gymnasium service provision, nightclub entertainment, restaurant service provision and accommodation. They are modified from (Khaloie, 2015), The dependent variable (guests' patronage) in the context of this study, takes a mono status but finds expression and manifestation in revisit intention and evaluated from the guests perspectives.The items were measured on a 5-point

Likert scale. It ranged from “Strongly Agree (SA=5)”, “ Agree (A=4)”, “Undecided (U =3), “Disagree (D=2), “Strongly disagree (SD=1)” on statements regarding guests’ evaluation of the integrated hospitality services provided by the luxury hotels and their patronage.

Data Analysis Techniques

Both descriptive and statistical inferential methods were used for this study. The descriptive methods include tables, frequencies, percentages, mean score and standard deviation. The statistical inferential method, on the other hand, was used to test the hypotheses. The multiple linear regression analysis was deployed for the test of hypotheses. This analytical tool is often used to examine the existence of the linear relationship between a dependent variable and a set of (more than two) independent variables (Onodugo, Ugwuonah& Ebinne,2010). For this study, the multiple linear regression analysis was adopted to determine the predictive power of the independent variable dimensions of integrated hospitality services in explaining guests’ patronage (dependent variable). The analysis involved the use of IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 21.0 to aid the statistical analyses.

4. ANALYSIS, RESULTS and FINDINGS

Respondents’ Demographic Profile

Section 1 shows the information on the category of visitors. The table revealed that (36) respondents (16%) were foreign while (192) respondents (84%) were domestic visitors. Section 2 shows the information on the type of visitors. The table revealed that (33) respondents (15%) were companies staff, (21) respondents (9%) were Government officials, while (174) respondents (76%) were independent visitors. Section 3 of Table 4.2 above shows the information on the length of stay. The table revealed that (78) respondents (34%) stay for 1 day while (122) respondents (54%) stay for 2 – 5 days. 28 respondents (12%) stayed for more than 5 days..

Section 2 shows the information on age brackets of the respondents. 48 respondents (21%), were within 18-30 years, 76 respondents (26%) were within 31–40 years, 88 respondents (39%) were within 41–50 years while 16 respondents (7%) were greater than 51 years. This information shows that majority of the respondents were within the ages of 31 – 40 years. Section 3 shows the marital status of respondents. 132 respondents (58%) were single, 81 respondents (36%) were married, 9 respondents (4%) were divorced, while 6 respondents (2%) are separated. Section 4 shows the gender of respondents. 147 respondents (64%) were male, while 81 respondents (36%) were female.

Section 5 shows the educational background of respondents. 62 respondents (27%) were pre-degree holders. 103 respondents (45%) were first degree holders. 48 respondents (21%) were second degree holders while 15 respondents (7%) possessed Ph.D and other qualifications. Section 6 shows the purpose of the visit. 81 respondents (36%) came for business, 70 respondents (31%) were on leisure/recreation, while 77 respondents (33%) came for Group meeting.

Section 7 shows the frequency of visit. 56 respondents (25%) were first-time visitors, while 172 respondents (75%) were repeat-visitors. Section 8 shows the travel party. 47 respondents (21%) travelled alone, 82 respondents (36%) travelled with family/partner, and 72 respondents (32%) travelled with friends / relatives, while 26 respondents (11%) travelled with organized groups. From this information, it shows that majority of the respondents traveled with families/partners.

Descriptive Analysis (Univariate Analysis)

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Gymnasium Services

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Functional fitness center with modern equipment	228	4.1529	1.46531
Guests exercising at the gym during visits	228	3.8141	1.20321
Helpful and courteous instructors at the centre	228	4.0537	1.45812
Valid N (listwise)	228		

Source: Survey Data, 2023 with IBM SPSS version 21

Information on Table 1 above shows the result of descriptive statistics on gymnasium services in the luxury hotels in Port Harcourt as perceived by guests through the application of IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 output. The mean scores of two items are greater than the criterion mean (threshold) of 3.9, meaning that most of the respondents agreed with all the three items of gymnasium services considering the fact that the grand mean of 3.9 > 3.0 mean score on five point Likert scale which is considered appropriate as regards acceptability. The implication is that the luxury hotels have functional fitness centre where guests can do physical exercises during their visits.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Nightclub Entertainment

Item Statistics			
Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Functional modern nightclub facility in the hotel	3.908	.49863	228
Provision of discoteque and karaoke musical show	4.221	.70323	228
Good DJs and courteous service personnel	4.0426	.57143	228

Source: Survey Data, 2023 with IBM SPSS version 21

Information on Table 2 above shows the result of descriptive statistics on nightclub entertainment services in the luxury hotels in Port Harcourt as perceived by guests through the application of IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 output. The mean scores of two items are greater than the criterion mean (threshold) of 3.9, meaning that most of the respondents agreed with all the three items of nightclub entertainment considering the fact that the grand mean of 3.9 > 3.0 mean score on five point Likert scale which is considered appropriate as regards acceptability. The implication is that the luxury hotels have functional nightclub where guests can unwind during their visits.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Restaurant Services

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Good quality catering /bar services available at hotel.	4.737	.50601	228
Availability of variety of foreign and local cuisines	4.0737	.63616	228
Services delivered by helpful and friendly employees	4.2053	.49536	228

Source: Survey Data, 2023 with IBM SPSS version 21

Information on Table 3 above shows the result of descriptive statistics on restaurant services in the luxury hotels in Port Harcourt as perceived by guests through the application of IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 output. The mean scores of the three items are greater than the criterion mean (threshold) of 3.9, meaning that most of the respondents agreed with all the three items of restaurant services considering the fact that the grand mean of 3.9 > 3.0 mean score on five point Likert scale which is considered appropriate as regards acceptability. The implication is that the luxury hotels have functional restaurant to meet guests' culinary needs.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on Accommodation

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Exquisite, clean rooms/suits/apartments with facilities	4.0851	.82909	228
Good room service delivery and in-door entertainment	4.3649	.84232	228
Convenient check-in and check-out process	4.1824	.82509	228

.Source: Survey Data, 2023 with IBM SPSS version 21

Information on Table above shows the result of descriptive statistics on accommodation in the luxury hotels in Port Harcourt as perceived by guests through the application of IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 output. The mean scores of the three items are greater than the criterion mean (threshold) of 3.9, meaning that most of the respondents agreed with all the three items of accommodation considering the fact that the grand mean of 3.9>3.0 mean score on five point Likert scale which is considered appropriate as regards acceptability. The implication is that there are good accommodation facility in the luxury hotels studied.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics on Luxury Hotel Guests' Patronage

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Willingness to revisit the same hotel in the future	228	4.2169	1.30342
First Choice hotel to revisit always in Port Harcourt	228	4.1149	1.19057
Not likely to switch to other hotels in the meantime	228	4.3304	1.19601
Valid N (listwise)	228		

.Source: Survey Data , DEC, 2023 with IBM SPSS version 21

Information on Table 5above shows the result of descriptive statistics on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt as perceived by guests through the application of IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 output. The mean scores of the three items are greater than the criterion mean (threshold) of 3.9, meaning that most of the respondents agreed with all the three items of guests patronage considering the fact that the grand mean of 3.9>3.0 mean score on five point Likert scale which is considered appropriate as regards acceptability. The implication is that the level of guests' patronage of the luxury hotels was considerable.

**Inferential Analysis (Hypotheses Test using Multiple Regression Analysis)
The Effect of Integrated Hospitality Services on Guests' Patronage**

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictive power of the independent variables in explaining guests' patronage. In other words, the test was conducted to examine which dimensions of integrated hospitality services has the most or the least significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt , Rivers State. The four (4)independent dimensions of integrated hospitality services as used in the context of this study are gymnasium services(GS), nightclub entertainment (NE), restaurant service provision and accommodation (A). Tables 5 to 8 outline the outcome of the multiple regression analysis between the integrated hospitality service dimensions and guests patronage in explaining our hypotheses results.

Table 6: Model Summary in Predicting Luxury Hotels Guests' Patronage

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.892 ^a	.796	.798	.44104

a. Predictors: (Constant), GS, NE, RS, A,.

Table 6.ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	99.304	7	12.186	30.902	.000 ^b
Residual	132.962	299	.445		
Total	232.265	306			

a. Dependent variable: Guests' Patronage

b. B .Predictors: (Constant), GS, NE, RS,, A.

Table 5 shows that R is .892, which means that the independent variables are 89.2% correlated with the dependent variable. R square is .796, this implies that the independent variable will explain 79.6% of the dependent variable while the other factors outside the model will account for the rest. The adjusted R square is .798. Simply put, the model summary is an indication that 79.6% of the variance in guest patronage can be explained by the changes in independent variables of integrated hospitality services. The R square statistic in the model is a measure used to measure the extent to which the total variation in the dependent variable is explained by the regression.

Table 6 shows that F-value is 30.902, which is greater than the mean square value (12.186), and the p-value is .000. As a general rule, this model is considered as a 'good fit' as it can explain above 60% (threshold) of variance in the dependent variable: (guests patronage) (Moosa & Hassan, 2015). What this means is that the regression model has made a significant fit with the data.

Table 8: Regression Analysis of Hypotheses test results for the Model Coefficients n =228

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.437	.517		2.782	.006
	Night clubEnt	.237	.077	.497	3.070	.002
	Gym.Serv.	.034	.045	.305	0.761	.000
	Rest.Serv	.298	.078	.558	3.438	.001
	Accomm.	.545	.136	.674	4.021	.000

a. Dependent variable: Guests' Patronage

b. b.Predictors: (Constant), NE, GS, RS, A,

Table 8 shows the result of the multiple regression analysis. All the 8 indicators of integrated hospitality services made significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable (guests' patronage). The first and most significant contributory variable that predicts guests patronage in the luxury hotels market scale is accommodation (Accom) ($\beta = .674, p=.000 < 0.05$). The second significant contributory variable that predicts guest patronage is restaurant service (ResServ) ($\beta = .558, p=.001$). The third significant predictive variable is nightclub entertainment (NEnt) ($\beta = .497, p=.002 < 0.05$) while the fourth contributory variable that predicts guests patronage is gymnasium service provision (GymServ) with positive beta value ($\beta = .305, p=.000 < 0.05$). As gleaned from their Beta and p-values in table 8, the model suggests that guests' patronage is a function of the degree of

contributions of each of the dimensions of integrated hospitality services. Thus, the model implies that changes in the quality of hospitality services can have significant influence on guests' patronage. The above information is summarized in the table below.

Table 9: Summary of Explanatory Powers of Integrated Hospitality Service Variables on Luxury Hotels Guests' Patronage
Regression Coefficients

Predictor Variables	Criterion Variable	Predictive Power β (Beta value)	P-Value	Level of Sig.	Significance of Effect of HIS on GP
Accom.	GP	.674	.000	$p=.000 < 0.05$	1 st Significant
Rest .Ser	GP	.558	.000	$p=.000 < 0.05$	2 nd Significant
NEnt,	GP	.497	.002	$p=.002 < 0.05$	3 rd Significant
GymServ	GP	.305	.000	$p=.000 < 0.05$	4 th significant

Table 10: Summary of Hypotheses Test Results using Multiple Regression Analysis of the Effects of Integrated Hospitality Services on Guests' Patronage

HP	Predictor Variables	Criterion Variable	Regression Co-efficient (Beta) Value	P-Value (sig.)	Level of Sig.	Decision
Ho 1	Gymnasium Serv.	GP	.305	.000	$p=.000 < 0.05$	<i>Reject Ho 1</i>
Ho 2	Nightclub Entertainment	GP	.497	.001	$p=.001 < 0.05$	<i>Reject Ho 2</i>
Ho 3	Restaurant Services	GP	.558	.001	$p=.001 < 0.05$	<i>Reject Ho 3</i>
Ho 4	Accommodation	GP	.674	.000	$p=.000 < 0.05$	<i>Reject Ho 4</i>

Table 10 shows that all the four dimensions of integrated hospitality services have a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt, thus, implying the rejection of all the null hypotheses.

5: Discussion of Findings

Effect of Gymnasium Service Provision on Guests' Patronage

The study also revealed a positive and significant effect of gymnasium services on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State as by the multiple regression test result ($\beta=.305$, $P\text{-value}=.000 < 0.05$). The above result is consistent with several studies such as Mzengi (2017) ; Christopher (2016) and Jennings (2007) which had established a positive and significant influence of gymnasium services on customer patronage in the recreational tourism and body building business sectors. Today, physical fitness and wellness is being promoted across the globe and hotels are making massive investment and out-sourcing in this regard. Luxury hotels attract high profile domestic and foreign customers who look forward to all-inclusive hospitality service provisions including gym services to optimize their experience which could serve as differentiation strategies for revenue generation improvement through patronage especially when it is provided alongside other hospitality service in one-stop setting which provides motion and monetary economies to the guests.

Effect of Nightclub Entertainment on Guests Patronage

The finding of this study also indicates that nightclub entertainment has a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria as reflected in the result ($\beta =.497$; $p=.001 < 0.05$). The result is consistent with previous studies which established that nightclub entertainment is an important feature of Night Time Entertainment (NTE) which has a positive and significant effect on guests satisfaction in the hospitality sector in several geographical locations of

the globe (Wang & Heng, 2019); Seaman & Horace, 2007; Kukoyi & Iwuagwu, 2018). The reason for the positive and significant impact of nightclub entertainment on guests' patronage of luxury hotels could be that most guests expect a good hotel to provide facilities that foster fun and relaxation. In these days of stress and strain in Nigeria, hotel guests that are young at heart perceive nightclub entertainment as a strategy to connect, socialize and unwind through dancing, and karaoke as well as other fun-sensitive activities which are veritable recreational practices. Therefore, the ability or inability of luxury hotel management to provide nightclub entertainment in addition to other hospitality offers under one roof can determine the level of guests' patronage or their switching behavior. Thus, the research finding has validated the proposition that nightclub entertainment has a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage.

Effect of Restaurant Service Provision on Guests' Patronage

The findings of this study indicate that restaurant service provision was a significant explanatory variable of luxury hotels guests' patronage and also associated positively and significantly with the guests' patronage as the result shows: ($\beta = .558; p = .000 < 0.05$). The result is consistent with previous studies (Abel, 2017; Babar & Rizwan, 2016; Adeoye & Babatunde (2015)). Commercial hospitality service involves warm and cordial reception and entertainment of guests and visitors with goodwill and liberality in an accommodation at a destination, as well as the provision of food, beverages and entertainment at a profit (Middleton & Clarke 2010).

Restaurant services in a hotel setting involve the delivery of food and beverages, and entertainment. Restaurants are responsible for providing food and beverages for tourists, even though some hotels do offer restaurant services also. The findings of this study can be justified by understanding that the availability of suitable restaurant services in a hotel that reflect cultural and religious diversities of guests in terms of differences in cuisines and health considerations in promoting sustainability in cuisine preparation has a significant influence on guests' patronage. What food and beverage is served, how it is served, by whom it is served and the environment in which it is presented has a significant effect on guests' patronage. With this finding, our hypothesis has been empirically substantiated.

Effect of Hotel Accommodation on Guests' Patronage

The current study finding shows that hotel accommodation had a positive and significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels Port Harcourt as depicted by our result: ($\beta = .674; p = .000 < 0.05$). This finding is consistent with previous studies carried out in various tourism market contexts in different geographical regions of the world such as Lacap (2014); Heyes et al. (2015); Khosravi et al. (2014).

The positive and significant influence of hotel accommodation on guests' patronage can be explained by the fact that accommodation has a multifaceted nature, having significant and innovative impact on the overall guest journey. Accommodation serves as the foundational pillar upon which the entire guest experience is constructed. Beyond providing a physical space for rest and sleep management, contemporary accommodation offerings are designed to align with the diverse preferences and expectations of modern travellers.

6. Conclusions and Implications

The findings that emerged from the univariate and multivariate analyses of the study suggested that most of the luxury hotels surveyed in the study actually provided integrated hospitality services (nightclub entertainment, gymnasium services, restaurant services, and accommodation) under one

roof. Guests' patronage of most of the luxury hotels surveyed was encouraging and growing at the time the study was being conducted. Multiple regression analysis showed that there were variations in the significance of contributions made the four (4) indicators of integrated hospitality services in explaining the dependent variable (guests' patronage). Hotel accommodation made the most significant contribution to explaining guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State ($\beta = .674; p = .000 < 0.05$). The second variable that generated significant effect on guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Rivers State was restaurant service provision ($\beta = .558; p = .001 < 0.05$). The third was night club entertainment ($\beta = .497; p = .001 < 0.05$) while the fourth was gymnasium service provision ($\beta = .305, p = .000 < 0.05$). Therefore, hotel accommodation, restaurant service provision, nightclub entertainment and gymnasium services were important factors in predicting guests' patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Consequently, the study concludes that the level of guests patronage of luxury hotels in Port Harcourt is a function of quality of integrated hospitality services provided by the fusion facility. Thus, poor quality of integrated hospitality service delivery will have a corresponding reduction in guests' patronage due to dissatisfaction. Consequently, revenue will drop with many attendant unpalatable consequences. In contrast, Maintaining or improving on the quality and standard of hospitality service delivery induces guests' patronage for corporate sustainability in the competitive hospitality industry. Integration or fusion of the various hospitality services in one facility (Fusion facility) in a guest-centric manner to optimize guests' experience in a cost effective way, therefore, becomes a competitive advantage.

However, in drawing our conclusion, we are very cautious and not unmindful about generalization of the research findings on the positive and significant contributions made by all the 4 indicators of integrated hospitality services in explaining or predicting guests' patronage, especially as the study was conducted during the 2023 Christmas festive season. Can the same study in an off-peak, non-festive period of the year produce the same result? This is a task for further research.

7. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommendations were put forth:

- i. The management of luxury hotels should maintain the current quality of room services and apartment to continuously enjoy guests' patronage.
- ii. The quality of conference and banquet materials should be improved on for guests' retention
- iii. Those luxury hotels that have converted their lounges to nightclubs should erect state-of-the-art nightclub entertainment facility.
- iv. They should increase their rental mix to include decoration and multi-media materials
- v. Guests should be taken on guided tour of all the amenities and informed of all the services available in the hotel. Information in a pamphlet or on the facility's website may not be very convincing. After all, seeing is believing.
- vi. Finally, loyalty programs should be introduced by the hotels whereby loyal guests are rewarded and appreciated for their patronage as a means of retaining them.

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